

**ПЕРСПЕКТИВИ МЕДИЧНОГО ЗАСТОСУВАННЯ
КАНАБІСУ У КОРОЛІВСТВІ МАРОККО**

**PROSPECTS OF MEDICAL APPLICATION
CANNABIS IN THE KINGDOM OF MOROCCO**

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The legalization of the medicinal and industrial uses of cannabis will greatly contribute to the protection of the farmers involved in cannabis cultivation and the improvement of their living conditions, which will benefit our country in general and the inhabitants of the northern regions in particular. This important step represents a response to the imperatives of social and scientific development. Furthermore, the legalization of this sector and its development must be based on a feasibility study that includes aspects that take into account the geographical, political, socio-economic, medical, and environmental context.

The development of cannabis legislation around the world is often complicated by the standards to be legalized, given the different types of cannabis products: molecule, mixture, dose, etc., which is why each country sets its own laws and standards. Limited medicinal use of cannabis is permitted in a number of countries, including states in the USA, Europe, Israel, Canada, and China. In Morocco, the success of the draft law on the legal medical and industrial uses of cannabis remains dependent on the synergy of efforts of all stakeholders to address the political, socio-economic, and environmental challenges in order to achieve development goals in the northern regions and promote public health services.

Similarly, it would be wise to learn from international experiences, especially from countries that represent a model for the legalization of cannabis.

In Morocco, there are more than 280 medicinal and aromatic plants whose components (leaves, flowers, fruits, and seeds) are used in many industrial fields (cosmetics, perfumes, spices, nutritional supplements, food, and medicine).

The uses of plants have varied over the ages and in different cultures, particularly in the Mediterranean.

Although the use of natural and medicinal plants is part of cultural heritage or tradition considered outdated, their application is still important in traditional medicine in developing countries and also in complementary and alternative medicine in industrialized countries, according to the World Health Organisation (WHO).

Studies conducted on the 280 most commonly used plants in Morocco have shown their effectiveness. The Atlas of Medicinal and Aromatic Plants of the Arab World also presents the most commonly used varieties.

Thanks to its climate, Morocco has a very wide variety of plant cover. As far as medicinal and aromatic plants are concerned, there are 4.200 types divided into 150 species and 940 categories. Of this total, only 280 plants are exploited at this stage.

This shortfall is attributable to shortcomings in terms of funding, valorization, and marketing of the products of scientific research. The budget allocated to scientific research does not exceed 1%, which is the minimum threshold recommended by competent international bodies. As far as valorization is concerned, it is still at the embryonic stage and much effort remains to be made in terms of legislation, regulations, and funding. It is, in a way, the missing link in the process that now needs to be institutionalized within the national research and innovation system.

Broadly speaking, the underdevelopment of this sector is explained by the insufficiency of scientific data relating to medicinal and aromatic plants, the absence of technical supervision, the unavailability of the advanced technologies necessary for its exploitation, and the absence of a database listing the biological and chemical properties of these plants and their uses.

Another constraint relates to poor management and lack of visibility in relation to traditional production outlets, which hinder the conquest of international markets.

All these factors mean that scientific research in the field is currently lacking and that we are unable to make the most of the products and put them at the service of our needs and priorities. The result, unfortunately, is a waste of human, material, and logistical resources.

On the other hand, it should be noted that data on medicinal and aromatic plants are scarce or, when available, are scattered. Hence the an urgent need to make an inventory and classification. This is really the preliminary step that must precede any strategy or action plan.

According to available figures, the annual production of aromatic and medicinal plants is estimated at 40.000 tonnes. Exports reach a value of 900 million dirhams while imports (derivatives with high added value) amount to 500 million DH.

Given its great potential, this sector is called upon to be an important lever of sustainable socio-economic development. The achievement of this objective requires the adoption of an appropriate scientific and technological approach as well as a greater openness of the University to its local environment to fully play its role regarding technical and applied research and monitoring the changes taking place in the world.

In this respect, the development of partnerships between laboratories and research centers in different countries is of great importance in order to face future challenges and to promote the development of this sector on the basis of an approach combining theoretical and technical aspects.

Hence the urgent need for the implementation of the Morocco Innovation Strategy and the strengthening of cooperation between Moroccan research structures in general and those specialized in aromatic and medicinal plants, in order to valorize and market the products derived from these plants. Our ambition, in the medium and long term, is to develop scientific research in the rules of the art which will allow the valorization of this precious heritage which is the pride of our country.

The rigorous scientific elaboration of the Atlas of Medicinal and Aromatic Plants of the Kingdom of Morocco has been completed and includes a monograph of 280 of the most commonly used plants, accompanied by studies and illustrative photos and enriched with their names, geographical distribution in Morocco and uses in traditional and modern medicine, with the inclusion of their chemical components and the consolidation of scientific references, whether they are related to botanical, agricultural, pharmaceutical, ecological or clinical studies. This is accompanied by five annexes, one of which includes the list of plants used for medicinal, aromatic, cosmetic, chemical, pharmaceutical, therapeutic, food, and agricultural purposes, while the other includes the names of the medicinal and aromatic plants used (medicinal name followed by the name in English, French and local Arabic and Moroccan names, as well as the geographical distribution).

It should be noted that the objective of the implementation of the Atlas of Medicinal and Aromatic Plants of the Arab World, of which only an introduction and a directory on medicinal and aromatic plants in Morocco have been published (pending the elaboration by each member region of the Federation of a manual of medicinal and aromatic plants of each country), The aim of the project was to develop and qualify the medicinal and aromatic plant sector in the Arab world and to make it a reference for students of agricultural, biological, chemical, medicinal and pharmaceutical specialities, given the lack of specialized training in this field in the faculties of medicine and pharmacy in most Arab countries.